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CUSTOMER PERCEIVED VALUE AND REPURCHASE INTENTIONS IN QUICK SERVICE RESTAURANTS (QSRs) IN PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The conceptualisation and delivery of memorable experiences to enhance customers' perceived value capable of promoting customers' behavioral intentions in the tourism industry have become a source of competitive advantage for tourism service providers such as the Quick Service Restaurants (QSRs). This current study examined the direct effect of customer perceived value on customers' repurchase intentions in QSRs in the garden city of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The descriptive survey research gathered data from 150 dinners in QSRs operating in Port Harcourt using a questionnaire with 12 items, in addition to four demographic items. Two hypotheses were developed and tested in the study and validated with the help of SPSS after data editing, with reliability analysis of the instrument and inferential statistics. The result of the inferential statistical analysis showed that repurchase intention towards the QSRs is driven by customer perceived value (emotional and social value). The study, therefore, concludes that a higher customer perceived value will engender higher repurchase intentions. This places a demand on owners/managers of QSR to develop a marketing strategy that will help them to identify, evaluate and manage customers' experiences in such a manner to enhance the pleasure of customers.

KEYWORDS

Emotional Value, Social Value, Repurchase Intention, Quick Service Restaurants.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is a global business that is characterized by intensive competition (Perdue, 2002; Ekeke&Olori, 2020). This places a demand on tourism service providers such as Quick Service Restaurants (hereafter called QSRs) to seek ways aimed at achieving competitive advantage through the understanding of needs and expectations of the target market. As argued by Kotler and Armstrong (2010), this objective could be achieved by marketers who develop tourism marketing strategies that are capable of delivering customer value with the objective of capturing value in return. In his own contribution, Rather, (2018) argued that the quest to achieve competitive advantage in the contemporary hospitality industry is to create excellent customer experiences which is the main source of differentiation strategy because of its ability to generate valuable customer relationships.

The foregoing confirms the fact that experience has assumed the product component in the competitive tourism/hospitality industry, in consonance with the paradigm shift from traditional marketing to experiential marketing (Pine & Gilmore 1999; Schmitt, 1999; Brakus, Schmitt, & Zarantonello 2009). However, deliverable hospitality experiences are expected to enhance the customer perceived value which is capable of producing synergistic effect to induce positive behavioural responses such as repurchase intentions.

Several empirical evidence exist in extant literature to prove that customer perceived value influences customer satisfaction and customer behavioural intentions in various market contexts (Raji & Zainal, 2016; Gallarza & Saura, 2006; Agarwal & Teas, 2001; Ashton, Scoot, Solnet & Breakey, 2010; Bojanic, 1996; Fang, 2006; Ryu, Han & Kim, 2008). There is no study to our knowledge that has attempted to empirically determine the effect of customer perceived value on customers' behavioural intentions. This current study attempts to fill the gap in literature by investigating the effect of customer repurchase intention towards QSRs in Port Harcourt, River State, Nigeria.

Theoretical Foundations

Means-End Theory

Academics of marketing extraction and practitioners in the field are conscious of the fact that the delivery of goods and service with high customer perceived value will induce customer satisfaction and positive behavioural outcomes. In addition, marketing managers of service brands such as QSRs are aware that any experiential value delivered to customers should be capable of enhancing customer perceived value which is capable of raising the prospects of repurchase intentions. All these efforts are always made because; the consumers/customers remain the final and ultimate arbiters. From the foregoing, the Means-End Theory (MET) provides the theoretical foundations to this study because consumers as goal-oriented decision-makers will always make purchase decisions that seem most likely to yield a more desirable end for them. The implication being that and services by a QSR that promotes customer perceived value will be attractive to diners. The foregoing explain why Olson and Reynolds (2001, p.3) noted that, the Means End Theory (MET) is based on the fact that, "decision makers choose courses of action (including behaviours such as purchase of particular brands) that seem most likely to achieve important outcomes" as its basic foundation.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Customer Perceived Value (CPV)

Customer perceived value (CPV) was defined by Woodruff (1997 p.142) as “customers perceived preference for and evaluation of those product attributes, attribute performances, and consequences arising from use that facilitate (or block) achieved the customers goals and purposes in use situation”. This definition of CPV is an attempt to offer explanation to the conceptualization of consumer perceived value by Zeithaml (1988). Zeithaml (1988 p.14) defined customer perceived value as, “the consumers overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perception of what is received and what is given”. Four principal though diverse meaning of value are contained in Zeithaml (1988) definition: value represents low price, what consumers want in a product, quality which consumers derive from a product for the price paid, and what consumers get (benefits) for what they give(sacrifice) (Raji & Zainal, 2016).

In extant marketing literature, there are two principal research approaches to the operationalization of the concept of perceived value: uni-dimensional and multi-dimensional approaches.

1. Uni-dimensional approach treats CPV as a one-dimensional construct. This implies that CPV could be operationalised as a single overall concept and “measured by a self-reported item (or set of items) that evaluates the consumer’s perception of value”. Empirical evidence showing where CPV was operationalised as a unit-dimensional construct includes Sweeny, Soutar and Johnson (1999), and Agrawal and Teas (2002).
2. Multi-dimensional approach conceives CPV as a multi-dimensional construct which is made up of “several interrelated attributes or dimensions that form a holistic representation of a complex phenomenon” (Sanchez –Fernandez & Iniesto–Bonillo 2007, p.431). Empirical evidence where CPV measured using this approach includes; Williams and Soutar (2000), Sheth, Newman and Cross (1991), and Sweeney and Soutar (2001).

Sweeney and Soutar (2001) categorised CPV into four types: functional value, economic value (price value), emotional value and social value. they could be described as follows.

1. Functional Value describes the perceived technical or practical benefits derived by customers using a goods or service. This value is concerned with utility which results from the actual performance of the goods/services.
2. Economic value describes customers’ cognitive trade-off between perceived benefits derived from good/ service and the monetary costs for using them.
3. Emotional value represents “the set of emotional responses elicited specifically during product usage or experiences, as described either by the distinctive categories of emotional experience and expression or by the structural dimension underlying emotional categories, such as pleasantness/unpleasantness, relaxation/action, or calmness/excitement” (Westbrook & Oliver, 1991 as cited in Raji & Zainal, 2016, p.60). In summary, this value is derived from feelings and pleasant experiences ().
4. Social value refers to “perceived utility acquired from an alternative association with one or more specific social groups” (Sheth, Newman & Gross 1991, p.160). The source of social value in QSR could occur when customers feel they are connected to other customers by dining in the same QSR.

Repurchase Intention

The concept of repurchase intention is very important to both practitioners and academics. To the marketing managers, repurchase intention of customers implies more sales and profitability, this explain why it is considered as one of the most important behavioural outcomes of consumers in marketing (Pharm & Train, 2014). The concept is defined by Young, Clark, and McIntyre (2007, p.92) as “the likelihood that a current customer of a restaurant expects to return in the future for a dining experience”. In addition, repurchase intention is defined by Ebrahim, Ghoneim, Irani, and Fan, (2013, p.1244) as “consumers’ decision about repeating the action of purchasing the brand”.

In extant literatures, it is argued that customers who return to rebuy from a particular supplier are deemed to have been satisfied from previous encounters/purchases. Such customers tend to spend more money through purchases, spread positive word of mouth, and remain loyal to the brand instead of switching to a competing brand (Mohsan, Nawaz, Khan, Shaukat, & Aslam, 2011). This implies that makes that managers of QSRs and their owners are expected to seek ways to enhance the level of customer satisfaction of their target market with a view to enhancing their rate of return for further patronage (Darley, Luethge, & Thatte, 2008).

Customer Perceived Value and Repurchase Intentions

Lait and Chiau, (2015) in the context of Malaysian hotel industry, investigated the antecedents of customer loyalty using 200 respondents at Kuala Lumpur International Airport (KLIA). The result showed that perceived service quality, perceived value, customer satisfaction and corporate image predicted customer loyalty significantly, while trust did not. Van Lierop, Badami, and El-Geneidy (2018) in the context of public transportation (airline), found that customer loyalty to an airline was associated with airline passengers’ perception of value for money, cleanliness and on-board safety, interaction with airline employees and image and feelings of commitment of the passengers towards public transport.

Rasoolimeinesh, et al (2020) in Iran found direct and positive effect of functional, emotional, and social values on customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry (traditional guest houses). Mohamed and Li (2017) in the context of cosmetics marketing in Malaysia found that both emotional and social value influenced consumers in their purchase decisions. In the restaurant market, Lglesias and Guillen (2004) found that perceived value had positive effect on customer satisfaction. Fang (2006), in the context of chain-restaurants found that service quality affected consumer value, recreational value and utility value positively.

With the foregoing empirical evidence, we suggest that the relationship between customer perceived value and repurchase intention towards QSRs will be positive and significant. This is based on the argument of Kang and Wang (2009, p.629), that, “operators care about customers’ patronage but not understanding that both service quality and perceived value are the pre-causes of the customer satisfaction and also the important impact factors on the customer patronage”.

We therefore expect that:

H1: The higher the emotional value a customer perceives, the higher the propensity to return to a QSR for re-patronage in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

H2: Social value has positive significant effect on customers' repurchase intention towards QSR in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Research Methodology

Research design: Descriptive research design was adopted for this current study. This is because data collections bothered on attitude, preference, behaviour and perception of customers of QRS.

Sample and data collection: Current dinners in the various (5) QSRs studied constituted the sample unit for the study. A well structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data were collected from customers of the QSRs in Port Harcourt. They were approached and urged to complete the questionnaire. Those who agreed were given a copy of the questionnaire to complete at their convenience while at the restaurants.

A sample size of 150 dinners got using Freund and William's formula for sample size determination from unknown population with 102 retrieved and found useful. The 102 useful questionnaires were subjected to data analysis.

Demographic Profile of Respondents: The profile analysis of the respondents showed that 54 respondents (53.5%) were male while 47 respondents (46.5%) were female. This implies that male respondents were of the majority. The information on age brackets of the respondent's shows that 17 respondents (16.8%), were less than 20 years, 54 respondents (53.5%) were within 20–29 years, 24 respondents (23.8%) were within 30–39 years while 6 respondents (5.9%) were greater than 40 years. This information shows that majority of the respondents were within the ages of 20 – 29 years. On educational qualification of respondents, the following were gotten: M.Sc (17) (16.8), B.Sc/HND (31) (30.7%), M.Sc/MBA/MA (29) (38.5%), , Ph.D (NIL), FSLC (NIL) and SSCE (31) (30.7%). From the information it shows that respondents with second degrees were of the majority. The analysis of the occupational status of respondents revealed the following: 55 respondents (54.5%) were Students, 37 respondents (36.6) were workers, while 9 respondents (8.9) were businessmen/women. This information implies that majority of the respondents were students.

Measurement Instrument and Questionnaire design

The major instrument for data collection was a well-structured questionnaire. A five-point Likert-type scale anchored by: Strongly Disagree [SD](1). Disagree [D](2), Agree [A](3), Agree fairly strongly(4) and Strongly Agree [SA](5) was used to represent the measurement items and to express the degree of agreement with the items or otherwise.

All the items were adapted from extant literature. The two dimensions of customer perceived value (emotional value and social value) were measured using items adapted from Sweeny and Soutar (2001), while items for repurchase intention were adapted from Jiang, Yang, and Jun (2012).

Research Results
Reliability Analysis

Table 1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.986	.986	12

The Cronbach Alpha of the 12-item research instrument was found to be .986 as shown in Table 1 above, thereby confirming its reliability. This value of, 986 is above the threshold value of .7 which was suggested by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994). This implies that the measuring instrument is internally consistent and could therefore be helpful and applicable in measuring opinions of customers of QSRs where the research focus was to determine the effect of customer perceived value on customers' repurchase intentions.

Discriminant Validity

Table 2 Correlation Matrix^a

	Emotional Value	Social Value	Repurchase Intention
Emotional Value	1.000	.789	.927
Correlation Social Value	.789	1.000	.829
Repurchase Intention	.927	.829	1.000

Table 2 above is a demonstration of the discriminant validity of the research instrument which is defined by Hair Jr, Black, Babin, and Anderson, (2010, p.126) as the "the degree to which two conceptually similar concepts are distinct". The result of the correlation matrix is in line with the suggestion of Fornell and Larker (1981) that discriminant validity occurs if the diagonal elements are higher than all the off-diagonal elements in their columns and rows.

Sampling Adequacy

Table 3 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.726
Approx. Chi-Square	306.974
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Df	3
Sig.	.000

The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) performed on 12 exploratory items of customer perceived value and repurchase intention as specified in the conceptual model in Figure 1 for the conduct of the KMO and Bartlett's Test is as shown in Table 3. The Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant at $p=0.000$ and KMO measure of sampling adequacy is .726. This value is greater than 0.5 which Kasser (as cited in Wong & Musa 2010, p. 3417) suggested as a minimum level.

Data Analyses

To ascertain the effect of customer perceived value and repurchase intention based on hypothesised relationships, multiple regression analysis was conducted.

Customer Perceived value and Repurchase Intention

Table 4 Multiple Regression analysis showing the effect of customer perceived value and repurchase intention in QSRS

Table 4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.940 ^a	.884	.882	.23292

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Value, Emotional Value

Table 5 ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	40.525	2	20.262	373.489	.000 ^b
1 Residual	5.317	98	.054		
Total	45.842	100			

a. Dependent Variable: Repurchase Intention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Value, Emotional Value

From the Tables 4 and 5 above, the following results are shown: adjusted R square = 0.882, F = 373.489 and $p=0.000 < 0.05$. This specifies that the two dimensions of customer perceived value (social value and emotional value) explains 88.2% variation in repurchase intentions in QSRS in Port Harcourt, Rivers State Nigeria. The outcome of analysis show that customer perceived value represented by the two dimensions had positive significant effect on repurchase intentions to the QSRS ($r = 0.940, p=0.000 < 0.05$).

Multiple Regression Analysis for dimensions of Customer perceived value (H1 and H2)

Table 6 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.131	.151		.870	.386
1 Emotional Value	.757	.059	.722	12.913	.000
Social Value	.214	.046	.259	4.627	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Repurchase Intention

Table 6 provides the multiple regression analysis for the contribution of the two dimensions of customer perceived value used in the study and hypothesised as H1 and H2 respectively. The table shows that un-standardized beta (β) of emotional value and social value sensory is: ($\beta = 0.757$), and ($\beta = 0.214$) respectively. This implies that emotional value made the greatest contribution to the research model.

The result of the regression analysis shows that both emotional value ($\beta = 0.757$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$) and social value ($\beta = 0.214$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$) provided by the QSRs in influencing their customers’ repurchase intentions made significant contribution to explaining the dependent variable. The two main hypotheses were therefore supported.

Therefore the model can be written as:

$$\text{Repurchase Intention} = 0.757(\text{EV}) + 0.214(\text{SV}) + .131.$$

The model suggests that by associating the two dimensions of customer perceived value (emotional value and social value) of a QSR, the empirical model can increase the level of customers’ repurchase intentions when other things remain constant. Accordingly therefore, changes in emotional and social value of each QSR can have the biggest influence on level of customers repurchase intentions.

Testing of hypotheses 1, 2 and 3

Decision Rule

If $PV < 0.05$ =Hypothesis is supported

$PV > 0.05$ = Hypothesis is not supported

H1: The outcome of analysis show that emotional value had significant effect on customers’ repurchase intentions to the QSRs in Port Harcourt ($\beta = 0.757$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$).

H2: The outcome of analysis show that social value had significant effect on repurchase intentions to the QSRs in Port Harcourt ($\beta = 0.214$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$).

Discussion of Results

Hypothesis 1 showed a significant effect of emotional value on customers' repurchase intentions towards QSRS in Port Harcourt ($\beta = 0.757, p=0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, H1 is supported. This finding is consistent with the findings of Raji and Zainal (2016) and Rasoolimeinesh, et al (2020)

Hypothesis 2 posited a significant effect of social value on repurchase intention at QSR in Port Harcourt. With $\beta = 0.214, p=0.000 < 0.05$, the effect is significant. This result is consistent with the prediction of H2 and is therefore supported. This finding is consistent with the finding of Mohamed and Li (2017).

Conclusion and Implications

The empirical study investigated the effect of customer perceived value on customers' repurchase intention at QSRS in the hospitality sector of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. A very important finding of the study is the fact that emotional value made the greatest contribution to the model ($\beta = 0.757, p=0.000 < 0.05$) followed by social value ($\beta = 0.214, p=0.423 < 0.05$). This could be attributed to the fact that an average QSR is designed and equipped to offer pleasurable experiences.

The fact that emotional value made the greatest contribution to the model shows that it is a very important determinant of customers' behavioural intentions such as revisiting the QSR for repatronage. The study therefore concludes that a higher customer perceived value will engender higher repurchase intentions. This implies that it is very critical for entrepreneurs managing QSR to identify, evaluate and manage customer's experiences in such a manner to enhance the pleasure of customers.

Limitations and Future Research

The fact that only QSRS were studied in this research effort possesses a limitation on the ability to generalise the research findings. Nigerians making up the sample units is equally a limitation. Future studies should focus on other service providers in the tourism industry with many nationals in Nigeria being part of the respondents.

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